

Clinical and Pathologic Features of Medial Calcific Sclerosis in the Prolapsed Uterus

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Abstract

Medial calcific sclerosis (MCS) of Monckeberg a nonocclusive calcification of the media of small to medium-sized muscular arteries, may frequently occur in the prolapsed uteri. The etiology and pathogenesis of MCS is still obscure. In the present investigation, we use routine hysterectomy specimen of prolapsed uteri to investigate age distribution, and localized vasotonic effect of parity. Systemic risk factors of hypertension and diabetes mellitus on atherosclerosis as well as on arteriolosclerosis are also investigated to see if there is any association with these and MCS in the prolapsed uterus. One hundred and fifteen cases of uterine prolapse are analyzed. The occurrence rate of MCS was 53.04% (61 of 115 cases). The mean age of MCS cases is 69.8 (SD=6.4), and cases without MCS, 54.5 (n=54, SD=7.6). [T-test : t=11.72, p=0.000, 95%CI=12.71-17.89]. The percentage of MCS increases positively with each 10-year age interval starting from age 50. No MCS is found in the 23 cases aged less than 50. [Extended Mantel-Haenszel test for trend: $\chi^2=44.766$ (DF=1), P=0.000]. Thus, we note that there is significant correlation of MCS and patient age, with an increasing trend of MCS as aging process continued past the age of 50. Significant difference was noted with MCS and parity between the two groups (5.01 vs. 3.28) evidenced by Chi-square test for relationship of the parity and MCS between parity of 3 or less and more than 3 [$\chi^2=22.924$, P=0.000]. No significant relationship was found for either hypertension or DM with MCS in the prolapsed uterus. Significant uterine weight loss was detected in those with MCS, when compared with non-MCS group [T-test: t=7.048, P=0.000, 95% CI (42.29-75.37)].

Lesion of MCS is a progressive degenerative change leading to smooth muscle necrosis of the media of small to medium-sized muscular arteries and superimposed calcium deposition. Smooth muscle cell necrosis or apoptosis with evident apoptotic bodies are diffusely present in media and may also be in intima. The investigation adds support to the prevailing concept that MCS in the prolapsed uterus is correlated to prolonged localized vasotonic influence as well as the aging process.

Key-words: medial calcific sclerosis, prolapsed uterus, intra-uterine arteries.

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Introduction

Medial calcific sclerosis (MCS) is an age-related degenerative process that leads to the calcification of the media of small to medium-sized muscular arteries that is fundamentally a different process from occlusive atherosclerosis (1, 2, 3). The vessels most commonly affected by MCS are the femoral, tibial, radial, ulnar, and uterine arteries (3). The coronary arteries are likewise subject to medial calcinosis (4). The genesis of arterial MCS is still obscure. According to prevailing concepts, medial calcification is related to prolonged vasotonic influences (3). Similar medial calcific lesions have been produced in experimental animals by repeated infusions of vasoactive pharmacologic agents such as epinephrine or nicotine (5). It is also thought that parity is prone to induce more stress and strain and leading to more wear and tear of the uterine arteries and might be a contributory factor in the etiology of MCS (7). A study by Bhagwat et al. (6) though, showed no significant difference in the average number of parity in the groups affected or not affected by medial calcification. Hypertension and diabetes mellitus (DM) may also have systemic vasotonic influence on intra-uterine arteries (1, 5). Uterine prolapse occurs not infrequently in aged women in gynecologic practice, and pathologists can frequently observe MCS of intrauterine arteries on routine check sections of the prolapsed uteri (6).

In the current study, we investigate

clinical and pathologic features of MCS in prolapsed uteri. We reviewed patients records for: age, probable localized and systemic risk factors of parity, hypertension and DM, available information of weight of the prolapsed uteri (from pathologic reports), and checked pathologic hematoxylin-eosin-stained sections of both uterine body and cervix. We wished to compare clinicopathologic relationships and clarify some issues about the etiology and pathogenesis of this entity.

Materials and methods

One hundred and fifteen cases of uterine prolapse undergoing hysterectomy during the 5 years between 1999 and 2003 were collected from pathologic files, we used routine histologic section slides with hematoxylin & eosin stains for investigation of the project. The procedure and sections for histology followed the guidelines from appendix A of Ackerman's surgical pathology, Vol.2, 7th edition for Uterus-Hysterectomy (General Instructions).

The measurement of severity of MCS of intra-uterine arteries is made by counting the number of sections with calcified artery, and the calcified arterial numbers on each section. The four levels used label arterial wall conditions from: normal through possibly advanced MCS of intra-uterine arteries were noted as below:

I- No evidence of degeneration or medial calcification.

II- Degenerative change of arterial wall

involving either intima or media.

III- Medial calcification of morphologically recognizable, aggregated calcific particles or patches, but not found in more than one tissue section, and less than half of arteries are involved in the tissue section.

IV- Advanced medial calcification being found in more than one tissue section, and or more than half of the arteries on any tissue section.

A pathologist then examined the histology of all the specimen sections from hysterectomy. This pathologist had no information on the case histories, in an attempt to lessen reviewer bias. Assumed risk factors for MCS including patient age, localized or systemic risk factors of parity, status of hypertension (including any history of cardiovascular episodes, 5 years or more of hypertension history with treatment, or with current blood pressure higher than 150/90 mmHg) and DM (5 years or more of known history with treatment, or currently blood sugar >110 of AC, or 140 of PC) were statistically correlated with medial calcification classification. Parity, status of hypertension and DM were tested with Chi-square test to see if there were any significant relationships between these assumed clinical risk factors and MCS of intra-uterine arteries. The average weight of the prolapsed uteri of both groups: medial calcification and non-calcification were also statistically tested (T-test) to see whether there was a significant relationship between

MCS and uterine weight.

Results

AGE-for the 115 cases of uterine prolapse average age was 62.6 years (range, 38-87; SD, 6.4). For those with calcification, 61 cases, the average age was 69.8 years (range, 57-87; SD, 6.4) and non-calcification, 54 cases, 54.5 years (range, 38-78; SD, 7.6). [T-test: $t=11.72$, $p=0.000$, 95%CI: 12.71 to 17.89] The occurrence rate of MCS among cases of uterine prolapse was 53.04% during this period of time. The occurrence rate of MCS increased with each 10-year age interval, starting from the age of 50 (Fig.1). No MCS was found in the 23 cases aged less than 50 years. [Extended Mandel-Haenszel test for trend: $\chi^2=44.766$ (DF=1), $P=0.000$ with 5 10-year age intervals].

Parity - information regarding parity was available for 113 the of 115 cases: 43 cases with parity of 3 or less, 10 of those identified with MCS, 33 with no evidence of MCS. 70 cases with parity of 3 or more: 50 cases with MCS of intra-uterine arteries and 20 without the lesion. Thus, we note a significant relationship with MCS of intra-uterine arteries in the prolapsed uteri between parity of less than 3 or more than 3. [Chi-square test: $\chi^2=22.924$, $p=0.000$]. Table 1 shows the relationship of parity with MCS in our prolapsed uteri cases.

Hypertension and DM - The information on hypertension and DM was available in 113 out of 115 case. Of the 60 cases with hypertension (53.10%), 34 had MCS, 26 had no evidence of MCS. Of the

Fig. 1. Percentage of occurrence of MCS increased with each 10-year age interval in the 5 age intervals in all cases.

53 cases without hypertension, 26 had MCS, 27 had no evidence of MCS. [Chi-square test: $\chi^2=2.332$, $p=0.127$]. Of the 36 cases with DM (31.86%), 22 had MCS, 14 had no evidence of MCS. Of the 77 cases without DM, 38 had MCS, 39 had no evidence of MCS. [Chi-square test: $\chi^2=0.931$, $P=0.335$]. Thus, neither hypertension nor DM revealed a significant relationship with MCS in the prolapsed uteri.

Weights of uteri - The data of weights of uteri were available in 112 out of 115 cases. (We note 1 uterine weight missing for a 70 year-old patient with MCS, and 2 were removed from the data due to extreme uterine weight, 536gm for a 48 year-old patient and 487gm for a 49 year old patient. They were removed for statistical calculation). The mean weight and SD of 60 prolapsed uteri with MCS was 46.13gm and

17.35gm, respectively. The mean weight and SD of 52 uteri without MCS was 104.96gm and 61.95gm, respectively.

Thus, prolapsed uterus with MCS was significantly correlated with the decrease in uterine weight. [T-test: $t=7.048$, $p=0.000$, 95%CI (42.29~75.37)].

Histology - Lesions of MCS are a progressive degenerative change with eventual smooth muscle necrosis of the media of small to medium-sized muscular arteries and superimposed calcium deposition. The media undergo degeneration that includes a variety of morphologic changes of basophilic, myxoid or mucoid, fatty or vacuolar ones. The accompanying similar intima degeneration with possible internal elastic lamellar damage, hyalinization and intima thickening is usually present. Fig.2 to Fig.4

show the serial progression of morphologic changes from level II (Fig.2) demonstrating basophilic and vacuolar changes in media and hyalinized intima thickening with foamy cells and cholesterol - like crystal deposition, Fig.3 shows a level III MCS lesion with precipitation of calcium particles and patches and intensive sclerosis from uterine cervix of an aged woman. Fig.4 is a composite of 4

panels showing MCS with cleft formation in media and circulatory stasis within vascular channels. Smooth muscle cell necrosis or apoptosis with evident apoptotic bodies are diffusely present in media as well as in intima. Table 2 shows the distribution of the 4 levels of arterial wall condition in the 115 cases of prolapsed uteri studied.

Fig. 2. Degenerative change of an intra-uterine artery (level II) involving both intima (asterisk) and media with apoptosis (arrow) of smooth muscle cells. (H&E stain, 200X)

Discussion

MCS is one of the most widespread types of arteriosclerosis. (8-14) It has not been associated with any particular pathological state. Follow-up studies have failed to show any clinically significant consequences, (4,15) and most authors comment that the patency of the vessel lumen is well maintained. In some selected groups of patients, the prevalence to MCS may be high, (6,8) and the disease has been shown to develop in younger individuals. (8) In our investigation of 115 cases of uterine prolapse, the occurrence rate was 53.04% and the mean age, 69.8 (range 57-87). This revealed a significant difference when compared with our non-MCS group that had a mean age 54.5 (range 38-78). [T-test: $t=11.72$, $P=0.000$, 95% CI (12.71-17.89)] That MCS is more prevalent in the older aged patient has been reported by most investigators. (6,9) Furthermore, in our study we document that the percentage of occurrence of MCS increased steadily with each 10- year age interval, starting from the age 50 (Fig. 1), while our results are similar to the investigation by Bhagwat RR et al. (6) To our knowledge, we are the first to document the correlation of MCS in the prolapsed uterus with the aging process, using the Extended Mandel-Haenszel test for trend.

Parity is considered to produce stress and strain resulting in the wear and tear of the intra-uterine vessels and might be a localized contributory factor in the etiology of MCS. The present study reveals

significant difference in the average number of parity in the group affected with MCS and that which did not evidence MCS (3.28 vs. 5.01). We did not use information concerning pregnancy as reported in records, because we do not think this kind of information is 100% reliable. Our data about parity is consistent with the prevailing concept of prolonged localized vasotonic influence, (10) but differs from the investigation of Bhagwat RR et al. (6) We can not ignore the potential of parity as a causal risk factor, for MCS in the prolapsed uteri, because women of the older generation in Taiwan used to have more children and pregnancies than women currently do now.

Hypertension and DM have been well established to be risk factors for atherosclerosis as well as for arteriolosclerosis. Whether both factors also play a role in MCS as a systemic contribution is not yet well studied. (16,17) Our present investigation did not determine any significant relationship between either factors and MCS in the prolapsed uteri.

Significant weight loss of uterus with MCS was noted when compared with non-MCS uterus [T-test: $t=7.048$, $P=0.000$, 95% CI (42.29-75.37)]. We excluded 2 uteri due to extreme weight from the group without MCS (536 gm & 487 gm, respectively) both younger patients. But the comparative difference of weights between both groups of uteri: those affected with MCS and those not affected by MCS was still very large (104.96 vs. 46.13 gm). MCS had been asymptomatic in our patients, and senile

atrophy of the uterus may be due to sexual hormone depletion. (6) But we can not deny the significant ischemic atrophy developed in the prolapsed uteri with MCS, which show evident rigid arterial wall and circulatory stasis, when compared with non-MCS group (Fig. 3 & 4). A related circulatory insufficiency inducing ischemic atrophy in the prolapsed uteri is also first reported, without mention of symptomatic effects of ischemia due to the non-occlusive lesion of MCS.

The severity of medial calcification in the prolapsed uteri did not reach any significant relationship with age, parity or uterine weight in current investigation.

Apoptosis with its pathogenesis in Monckeberg's sclerosis and atherosclerosis was investigated by Schoppet M et al. (18) In our cases of prolapsed uterus with MCS, smooth muscle cell necrosis or apoptosis with evident apoptotic bodies are diffusely present in media as well as in intima. We highlight areas of apoptosis requiring further investigation.

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Fig. 3. Well-formed medial calcification (asterisk) superimposed to degenerative wall of an intra-cervical artery (level III) from an aged woman, clusters of apoptotic bodies (arrow) of smooth muscle cells being evident. (H&E stain, 200X)

Fig. 4. Composite of 4 panels showing an intra-uterine artery with advanced MCS forming cleft (asterisk on panel A & C), degenerative change with apoptosis (arrow on panel C & D) of smooth muscle cells is evident. Panels A and B also show circulatory stasis with packed red blood cell aggregation. This patient had more than one tissue section showing diffuse medial calcification of intra-uterine arteries (level IV). (Panels A & B, H&E stain, 100X; C & D, H&E stain, 200X)

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Table 1. Average number and range of parity in relation to MCS as well as non-MCS in the prolapsed uteri.

Group	No.of cases	Parity	
		Range	Average parity
With MCS	60	0-12	5.01
Without MCS	53	0-8	3.28

Table 2 Distribution and related rate of arterial wall conditions including degenerative change and varying degree of MCS of intra-uterine arteries in the prolapsed uteri studied

Pathological Conditions	Total No. of Cases	Arterial Wall Conditions			
		I*	II*	III*	IV*
		Number/ Percentage	Number/ Percentage	Number/ Percentage	
Prolapsed Uterus	115	22 / 19.13	32 / 27.83	17 / 14.78	44 / 38.26